

Defining the sonochemical threshold for phase-pure Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle synthesis

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ABSTRACT

This study systematically examines the sonochemical synthesis of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles as a function of precursor concentration, alkalinity, reagent-addition mode, and effective irradiation time. The central result is that complete Fe(OH)₂ conversion into Fe₃O₄ during sonication determines phase purity and reproducibility. When this threshold is not reached, residual precursor continues to transform during post-synthesis handling, so washing acts not as a passive purification step but as a secondary conversion stage in incompletely converted systems. For phase-pure samples obtained after complete sonochemical conversion, faceted Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with tunable sizes from 18(6) to 60(20) nm were reproducibly obtained. In these samples, SLP follows the expected size dependence under fixed AMF conditions. In contrast, for incomplete sonochemical conversion systems, the evolving Fe₃O₄ fraction makes SLP normalization unstable, and the absorbed power normalized by total iron (SPI) provides a more robust metric. Across these dynamic systems, SPI correlates with XRD microstrain, indicating that structurally defective secondary magnetite formed during post-irradiation conversion correlates to heating efficiency. These results define the process window required for reproducible sonochemical Fe₃O₄ synthesis and clarify how incomplete precursor conversion biases both structural and hyperthermia analyses.

1. Introduction

Sonochemistry routes are widely used to enhance reaction rates and control the nanomaterial formation through high-energy chemistry induced by acoustic cavitation [1–4]. By creating microsecond “hot spots” ($T \approx 5000$ K, $P \approx 500$ atm) and high-velocity interparticle collisions [5,6], ultrasound enables precise control over their size, shape, and crystallinity [3,7–9]. Despite its broad versatility [10–12], the specific application of sonochemistry to Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) synthesis remains characterized by a significant lack of parametrization [13–16]. For instance, most aqueous protocols feature highly variable iron salt precursor concentrations and base addition timing during ultrasonic irradiation [17–19], while several reported methods require post-synthesis thermal treatment to crystallize amorphous precipitates [20,21]. Moreover, many studies omit detailed information on effective irradiation times, resulting in MNPs with low crystallinity, broad size

distributions, and secondary phases. Maintaining such control is crucial for ensuring that these greener synthesis methods remain reproducible at scale.

From a chemical perspective, the addition of FeSO₄·7 H₂O to NaOH solution leads to the instantaneous precipitation of Fe(OH)₂ ($K_{sp} = 10^{-17}$ – 10^{-16}) [22,23]. High-intensity sonication drives the sonolysis of water, producing reactive free radicals ($H_2O \rightarrow \bullet H + \bullet OH$) [24] and a Fenton-like redox environment ($2 \bullet OH \rightarrow H_2O_2$) where H₂O₂ facilitates the rapid oxidation of Fe²⁺ (k_1) and slower reduction of Fe³⁺ (k_2): [25–27]

Because $k_1 \gg k_2$, this environment dictates the final stoichiometry of

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the nanoparticles. While omitting the base leads to a long-term maghemite formation [28], the presence of a base has been shown to be as influential, if not more so, than the radicals generated as expected from a coprecipitation-like synthesis [29].

Building on this background, we systematically investigated how precursor concentration, alkalinity, reagent-addition mode, and effective irradiation time determine the phase-purity of sonochemical Fe₃O₄. We demonstrate that the incomplete sonochemical conversion of the Fe(OH)₂ precursor is a relevant, yet overlooked, variable. We show that partial precursor consumption leads to the unintended formation of secondary Fe₃O₄ during post-synthesis handling, directly impacting the reproducibility and heating performance of the resulting MNPs. By identifying the thresholds for complete sonochemical conversion, we decouple intrinsic ultrasonic chemistry from post-synthesis transformations, providing a standardized framework for sonochemical MNP production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

The reagents employed in the synthesis were iron (II) sulphate heptahydrate (FeSO₄•7 H₂O ≥ 99%) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH ≥ 97%), both purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and without further purification. Ultrapure water (Milli-Q grade, resistivity 18.2 MΩ·cm⁻¹ at 25 °C) was used for all solution preparations and washing steps. Ethanol (97%, analytical grade) was also used as received for selected washing procedures and dispersion tests. Commercial bovine gelatin (Royal®) was used as the dispersing medium for hyperthermia measurements. Hydrochloric acid (HCl 37%, Labbox, Spain), nitric acid (HNO₃, 65%, Panreac), and ammonium thiocyanate (NH₄SCN, Merck) were employed for iron quantification.

2.2. Nanoparticle synthesis

Fe₃O₄ MNPs were obtained using a commercial ultrasonic processor (UP400St, Hielscher Ultrasonics GmbH, Germany) equipped with a titanium sonotrode (S24d22D) operated in Power mode (400 W, 100% amplitude and clock ratio; see Fig. S1 for energy and temperature profiles). Different samples were produced by systematically varying FeSO₄ concentration, NaOH concentration/injection time, and effective irradiation time. The synthesis followed a three-stage ultrasonic protocol using either a 100 mL or 250 mL low-form beaker (for 50 mL and 100 mL batches, respectively) with the sonotrode held at ≈ 10 mm from the beaker base (resulting in ≈22 mm and ≈35 mm immersion depths, respectively): 1) The initial FeSO₄•7 H₂O solution was pre-irradiated

(t_{pre}) from 5 to 75 s. 2) The NaOH was premix or injected (t_{inj}) at a fix rate (10 mL·min⁻¹) for 60 s under continuous sonication. 3) The effective irradiation (t_{eff}) of the final alkaline mixture continued from 240 to 1740 s. A schematic illustration of the standardized process is shown in Fig. 1, and the values for the different parameters are shown in Table 1 below. Due to the high thermal energy generated during sonication (≈90 °C peak, Fig. S1 D-F), Milli-Q water was added (1 mL·min⁻¹) after the 20th minute of irradiation to compensate for evaporative losses.

Three different separation protocols were evaluated to isolate the magnetic precipitate from the supernatant: (i) centrifugation (13,910 ×g, 15 s) followed by magnetic retention of the pellet and redispersion in Milli-Q water assisted by ultrasonic bath; (ii) centrifugation followed by magnetic retention and manual pipette redispersion; and (iii) magnetic decantation waiting until a colorless liquid was observed and manual redispersion. In samples that did not reach complete conversion during sonication, these washing/redispersion steps may also promote further transformation of residual Fe(OH)₂ and therefore should not be interpreted as purely passive purification.

For clarity, samples were classified to the conversion state of the as-prepared product and the application of a post-synthesis washing step. Three groups were defined: G1, complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed: S022, S023, S024, S027, S032; G2, incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed: S018, S019, S020, S021, S030, S031; G3, incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed: S011, S018_L, S019_L, S020_L, S021_L. G1 includes samples synthesized under conditions that yielded XRD-phase-pure Fe₃O₄ directly in the as-prepared state, without post-synthesis washing. G2 includes as-prepared samples in which XRD still detected residual oxyhydroxide phases, indicating incomplete precursor conversion. G3 includes samples initially obtained under incomplete sonochemical conversion conditions and subsequently subjected to the washing treatment, which increased the Fe₃O₄ fraction through removal and/or conversion of residual Fe(OH)₂.

2.3. Characterization of nanoparticles

2.3.1. Crystallographic structure

Structural characterization of the samples was done with an X-ray diffractometer (PANalytical Empyrean XRD), using Cu Kα radiation (λ = 0.1540 nm) at room temperature. The samples were prepared by depositing a concentrated precipitate suspension (in synthesis solution or Milli-Q water) onto a rounded glass substrate and allowing the liquid to evaporate completely. Lattice parameters (*a*), apparent crystallite sizes (*d*), microstrain (ε), and effective Fe₃O₄ fraction (φ_{XRD}) were determined through Rietveld refinement using the FullProf Suite. A LaB₆ standard was used to determine the Instrumental Resolution Function (IRF).

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the three-stage sonochemical synthesis protocol for Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles. The synthesis is controlled by three distinct time intervals: the pre-irradiation time (t_{pre}), the alkaline solution injection time (t_{inj}), and the effective irradiation time (t_{eff}) after NaOH addition.

Table 1

Experimental parameters screened for the sonochemical synthesis of Fe₃O₄ MNPs. Symbols: precursor mass (m); synthesis volume (V); pre-irradiation time (t_{pre}); NaOH injection time (t_{inj}); effective irradiation time (t_{eff}); total time (t_{tot}); and effective Fe₃O₄ fraction in the as-prepared product estimated from XRD (ϕ_{XRD}). The column "As-prepared conversion status" indicates whether phase-pure Fe₃O₄ was obtained directly after sonosynthesis. All syntheses were initiated at room temperature, except for sample S020.

Sample	Precursor	m (mmol)	V (mL)	t _{pre} (s)	t _{inj} (s)	t _{eff} (s)	t _{tot} (s)	ϕ _{XRD} (%)	As-prepared conversion status
Control	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	50						
	NaOH	8.2							
S011	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	50			60	60	100	Incomplete
	NaOH	8.2							
S018	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	50			600	600	50	Incomplete
	NaOH	8.2							
S019	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	45	5		480	540	50	Incomplete
	NaOH	8.2							
S020	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	90	30		240	330	< <80	Incomplete
	NaOH	20.0							
S021	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	50			330	330	< <80	Incomplete
	NaOH	20.0							
S022	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	0.4	90	75		525	660	100	Complete
	NaOH	20.0							
S023	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	0.8	90	60		600	720	100	Complete
	NaOH	20.0							
S024	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	1.2	90	60		600	720	100	Complete
	NaOH	20.0							
S027	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	0.4	90	60		540	660	100	Complete
	NaOH	19.9							
S030	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	90	60		540	660	36.5	Incomplete
	NaOH	20.0							
S031	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	90	60		1140	1260	71.1	Incomplete
	NaOH	20.0							
S032	FeSO ₄ ·7 H ₂ O	4.0	90	60		1740	1860	100	Complete
	NaOH	20.0							

2.3.2. Morphology and size

The morphology and size distribution of the nanoparticles were determined by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) using a Tecnai T20 operated at 200 kV. TEM samples were prepared by dropping a diluted (translucent) nanoparticles suspension onto a carbon copper grid. Size histograms were obtained from randomly labeled nanoparticles using ImageJ software, and the mean diameter and standard deviation were estimated by fitting log-normal distributions.

2.3.3. Chemical composition

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer) measurements were performed in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode, by applying a 2 µL concentrated sample suspension directly onto the ATR crystal. The spectra were recorded as volatile substances evaporated. To investigate possible Fe(OH)₂ conversion into Fe₃O₄ during washing steps, a control solution was freshly prepared without any ultrasonic treatment, by dissolving 4 mmol of FeSO₄·7H₂O and 8.167 mmol of NaOH (2% molar excess relative to the 1:2 Fe²⁺:OH⁻ stoichiometry for Fe(OH)₂ formation). The resulting mixture was subsequently washed several times to evaluate precipitate evolution under these conditions.

2.3.4. Iron quantification

The iron content was quantified by the thiocyanate colorimetric method using a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1280). The iron content samples were completely dissolved in 500 µL of HNO₃ (14.1 M) and 500 µL of HCl (6 M), and the solution was left overnight to ensure full oxidation to Fe³⁺. Following, a 55 µL aliquot of the resulting Fe³⁺ solution was mixed with 445 µL of HCl (6 M) and 500 µL of NH₄SCN (1.5 M). The iron(III) thiocyanate complex ([FeSCN]²⁺) UV-Vis spectra were recorded, and the absorbance at the characteristic wavelength of ≈ 486 nm was measured and compared against a pre-established calibration curve to determine the total iron concentration.

2.3.5. Magnetic heating

Magnetic heating experiments were performed using a commercial applicator (nB Nanoscale Biomagnetics) at different frequencies ($f = 140, 320$ and 760 kHz) and magnetic field amplitudes ($120 \leq H_0 \leq 560$ G). Before each heating experiment, the temperature of the sample was left to reach thermal equilibrium with room temperature. Temperature measurements were done using an RF-immune temperature sensor (Neoptix T1®).

It is worth noting that, for the type of samples involved in this study, direct comparison of the Specific Loss Power (SLP) between different samples can be misleading, since each sample contained different amounts of constituent phases, some of which do not contribute to the heating mechanism. Therefore, in these samples with different Fe-O phases we analyzed their heating power from the calorimetric relationship $Q = mc\Delta T$ and the maximum derivative:

$$P = (m_L c_L + m_{MNP} c_{MNP}) \left(\frac{dT}{dt} \right)_{\max} \approx m_L c_L \left(\frac{dT}{dt} \right)_{\max} \quad (3)$$

where P is the power absorbed by the entire sample (converted into heat), m_L and m_{MNP} are the mass of the carrier liquid and the magnetic nanoparticles, respectively, c_L and c_{MNP} are the specific heat capacity of the liquid and the magnetic nanoparticles, respectively, and the term $(dT/dt)_{\max}$ represents the maximum rate of temperature increase observed at the very beginning of the heating curve. In all cases, the concentration of MNP used was such that $m_L c_L \gg m_{MNP} c_{MNP}$ and thus the latter term could be neglected. The maximum rate of temperature increase was extracted from the slope of the heating curve within the first 70 s of the experiment.

The Specific Loss Power (SLP) values assigned to the magnetic phase (Fe₃O₄) were calculated in the usual way with the expression:

$$SLP = \frac{P}{m_{Fe_3O_4}} = \frac{m_L c_L}{m_{Fe_3O_4}} \left(\frac{dT}{dt} \right)_{\max} \quad (4)$$

where the $m_{Fe_3O_4}$ refers to the mass of Fe₃O₄ MNPs only.

Additionally, we defined the Iron Specific Power per Iron Mass (SPI)

as the power absorption normalized by the total mass of atomic iron (m_{Fe}), irrespective of the phase in which the iron is present (SPI = P/m_{Fe}). This metric was introduced because, in incomplete sonochemical conversion samples, the Fe_3O_4 fraction continues to evolve during post-synthesis handling and gelatin dispersion. In these dynamically evolving systems, SLP normalized by a fixed XRD-derived Fe_3O_4 fraction can misrepresent the actual magnetic mass present at the moment of measurement. Consequently, SLP remains appropriate for static, well-defined Fe_3O_4 sonochemical products, SPI serves as a more robust comparative metric for tracking total heating efficiency without the uncertainty of a fixed conversion ratio.

All power loss measurements were performed by dispersing the samples in bovine gelatine. A control gelatine solution (1 mL of 10% w/v pure gelatine without NPs) was measured to account for potential heating artifacts arising from the experimental setup, such as heat transfer from the coils to the sample environment. A non-zero initial temperature increase was observed in this control, suggesting an external heating contribution. Therefore, the maximum rate of temperature increase observed in the gelatine control under the same AMF conditions was subtracted from the $\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{max}$ values obtained for all nanoparticle-containing samples.

SLP measurements were performed in MNPs immobilized in a 0.5% w/w gelatin matrix. A 10% w/v gelatin solution was first prepared at 80 °C. Approximately 5 mg of freshly magnetically decanted wet precipitate was weighed into 2 mL HPLC glass vial, followed by the addition of 1 mL of the gelatin solution. Homogeneous dispersion was achieved via pipetting and ultrasonication in a 70 °C bath (< 30 s), after which the samples were rapidly cooled to prevent nanoparticles sedimentation.

A control solution was freshly prepared to investigate the potential heating contribution of the oxyhydroxides in solution. This involved dissolving 161.5 μ mol of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and 323.9 μ mol of NaOH (representing a 2% molar excess of NaOH relative to the 1:2 $Fe^{2+} : OH^-$ stoichiometry required for $Fe(OH)_2$ formation) in 1 mL of Milli-Q water. The heating curves of this solution were measured under three different conditions: i) the initial aqueous solution (Control_W), ii) after the addition of 63.3 mg of gelatine powder (resulting in a 6.33% w/v gelatine concentration), mixed with brief room temperature sonication (< 10 s) and cooled to avoid precipitation (Control_G), and iii) after further sonication of the gelatine solution at 65 °C for 3 min and frozen to avoid precipitation (Control_GT).

2.4. Statistical analysis of experimental parameters

The relationship between the various synthesis and structural parameters was quantitatively assessed using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (ρ). A ρ value of +1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect inverse correlation, and 0 indicates no linear correlation. This analysis was applied to the numerical variables within the previously defined sample groups to identify the strength and direction of linear relationships.

3. Results

Table 1 summarizes the experimental parameters investigated across the series of sonochemical syntheses of Fe_3O_4 . Under the specified ultrasonic irradiation conditions, the process typically yielded a grayish precipitate with varying degrees of magnetic responsiveness, with the notable exception of samples S022, S023, S024, S027 and S032, which exhibited immediate magnetic behavior. The three separation protocols employed to isolate the precipitates produced comparable outcomes: the magnetic susceptibility of the solid phase increased noticeably with successive washing cycles. Simultaneously, the supernatants remained colorless and showed a progressive reduction in pH toward neutrality (Fig. S2).

To investigate the origin of this evolving magnetic response, a control experiment was conducted by direct mixing $FeSO_4$ and NaOH in aqueous solution without ultrasonic irradiation. The stoichiometric precipitation of the precursor follows:

Initially, this process formed a greenish, non-magnetic precipitate. However, as the washing cycles progressed, involving the decantation and replacement of the colorless supernatant, a systematic increase in magnetic responsiveness was observed. This was accompanied by a significant reduction in the apparent precipitate volume and a distinct color transition from greenish to black. The visual sequence of these magnetic and colorimetric changes is documented in Fig. S3.

3.1. FTIR spectroscopic analysis

FTIR measurements were employed to monitor the phase evolution of incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed S019 sample, comparing the initial precipitate to the control and the final washed state (Fig. 2).

A significant reduction in the band at 1126 cm^{-1} (SO_4^{2-}) [30,31] was observed as early as the second wash (Fig. 2 B, S4). The low-intensity feature near 1640 cm^{-1} is attributed to the H–O–H bending mode of adsorbed water, which decreases along with the O–H stretching vibrations (around 3400 cm^{-1}) throughout the washing cycles [32]. Simultaneously, a progressive intensification of the 574 cm^{-1} band (Fe–O stretching in the spinel structure) [29,33] occurred. The evolution of the hydroxyl content was characterized by a shift in the peak depth ratio of OH:Fe–O from approximately 1:5 in the unwashed state to 1:25 by the 10th wash (Table S1).

The spectra for the control and the unwashed S019 were similar, though a slight narrowing of the O–H stretching vibrations was noted. As washing proceeded, these O–H contributions decreased while Fe–O stretching bands intensified. By comparing the spectra of complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed samples (S023–S027, S032) closely resemble the 10th wash spectrum of S019 (Fig. 2 C), featuring dominant Fe–O bands and a residual O–H signal [7].

3.2. Crystallographic analysis

3.2.1. Incomplete sonochemical conversion

XRD patterns of incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed samples S018 (pre-mixed reactants) and S019 (delayed NaOH injection), synthesized under neutral pH conditions, were recorded in both unwashed and washed states (Fig. 3 b,c). In the unwashed state, both samples exhibited a multi-phase composition consisting of Fe_3O_4 (space group $Fd\bar{3}m$, COD 1539747) [34], orthorhombic lepidocrocite (γ - $FeOOH$, space group $Cmcm$, COD 9017417) [35], and at least one unidentified intermediate hydroxide phase. The γ - $FeOOH$ phase showed a distinct preferential orientation along the (020) direction, identified and accounted for during the Rietveld refinement (see Fig. S5 for detailed fits). In this initial state, Fe_3O_4 accounted for $\approx 50\%$ of the crystalline content.

Following the washing process, the XRD patterns for the incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed counterparts (S018_L and S019_L) transitioned to a single-phase spinel structure. This was accompanied by a shift in the lattice parameter toward maghemite-like values ($a < 8.39 \text{ \AA}$) and the disappearance of the secondary phases [36]. A similar trend was observed for S011 (pre-mixed reactants, Fig. 3 a), despite having the shortest irradiation time. Table 2 summarizes the parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinement for all samples.

The XRD patterns of incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed samples S020 (delayed NaOH injection) and S021 (pre-mixed), revealed distinct phases compared to the neutral pH series (Fig. 3 b,c). While Fe_3O_4 was present, it was found alongside a predominance of secondary

Fig. 2. Illustrative FTIR Spectroscopic Analysis of Precursor Conversion. All spectra are normalized to the Fe-O stretching band ($\approx 570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for comparison. (A) Illustrates the proposed two-step conversion: initial sonochemical formation of a weakly magnetic $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ -rich precipitate, followed by the complete conversion to Fe_3O_4 during subsequent washing steps. (B) Compares the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ -rich control solution and the initial S019 sample (incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed) with subsequent washing stages of S019. (C) Compares the fully washed S019 sample (10th wash) against five distinct magnetite samples achieved through complete sonochemical $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion.

Fig. 3. Comparative X-ray diffractograms from sonochemical synthesis of Fe_3O_4 NPs. Incomplete sonochemical conversion: (a) S011 (washed); (b) S018 (unwashed) and S018_L (washed); (c) S019 (unwashed) and S019_L (washed); (d) S020 (unwashed) and S020_L (washed); (e) S021 (unwashed) and S021_L (washed); (f) S022, S023, S024, S027 and (g) S032. All diffractograms are normalized with respect to the (311) reflection and Miller indices (hkl) corresponding to the cubic spinel structure $\text{Fd}\bar{3}\text{m}$ are indexed. Non-indexed reflections in unwashed samples correspond to the identified intermediate phases ($\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$, $\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$, and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$) or to unresolved residues that serve as qualitative indicators of phase impurity below the sonochemical threshold.

phases.

Following the washing procedure, incomplete sonochemical con-

version samples S020_L and S021_L (Fig. 3 d,e) reached a partial conversion to Fe_3O_4 ($\approx 80\%$). The remaining crystalline fraction consisted of residual ferrous hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$, space group $\text{P}\bar{3}\text{m}1$, COD 1008762) ($\approx 15\%$) [37], and goethite ($\alpha\text{-FeO}(\text{OH})$, space group Pbnm , COD 9002158) ($\approx 5\%$) remaining [38]. Compared to neutral pH syntheses (S011-S019_L), these high-alkalinity samples exhibited a lower microstrain (ϵ) and a lattice parameter closer to stoichiometric magnetite ($a \approx 8.39 \text{ \AA}$) [34].

3.2.2. Complete sonochemical conversion

The impact of ultrasonic irradiation time was examined via XRD patterns of samples S030-S032 (delayed NaOH injection at 60 s), synthesized at standard concentration (Fig. 3 g). At 10 min of irradiation (S030), the crystalline content consisted of Fe_3O_4

(36.5%), goethite (33.8%), and ferrous hydroxide (29.7%). Extending irradiation to 20 min (S031) resulted in a Fe_3O_4 yield of 71.1%, with goethite and ferrous hydroxide fractions reduced to 16.1% and 12.8%, respectively. At 30 min (S032) yield transitioned to a single-phase spinel structure.

Alternatively, the effect of varying precursor concentration at a fixed irradiation time (10 min) was evaluated (samples S022-S027, delayed NaOH injection 60 s). Under these conditions, lowering the initial precursor amount (0.4–1.2 mmol) resulted in XRD patterns consistent with single-phase Fe_3O_4 (Fig. 3 f). This series produced significantly smaller crystallite sizes (e.g., 15 nm in S022 compared to 41 nm in S032) without detectable $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ byproducts in the unwashed state.

3.3. Morphological analysis

3.3.1. Incomplete sonochemical conversion

While XRD analysis provided information on the crystalline phase, apparent crystallite size and strain, TEM was employed to observe the morphology and size distribution of the synthesized nanoparticles. TEM

Table 2

Structural parameters obtained from Rietveld refinement of powder XRD patterns and mean sizes obtained from TEM analysis. Samples are classified as complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (G1), incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (G2), and incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed (G3). Symbols: lattice parameter (a); average apparent size ($\langle d \rangle$); microstrain (ϵ); effective Fe_3O_4 fraction in the as-prepared product estimated from XRD (ϕ_{XRD}); mean size ($\langle d_1 \rangle$); standard deviation (σ_1); second population mean size ($\langle d_2 \rangle$); second population standard deviation (σ_2).

Sample	Description	XRD				TEM			
		a (Å)	$\langle d \rangle$ (nm)	ϵ (%)	ϕ_{XRD} (%)	$\langle d_1 \rangle$ (nm)	σ_1 (nm)	$\langle d_2 \rangle$ (nm)	σ_2 (nm)
S011	G3	8.383	32	0.25	100	40	20		
S018	G2	8.387	49	0.24	50	50	10		
S018_L	G3	8.379	68	0.41	100	80	20		
S019	G2	8.388	52	0.28	50	60	20		
S019_L	G3	8.377	83	0.36	100	40	20	80	20
S020	G2	8.385				50	10		
S020_L	G3	8.394	32	0.05	80	50	30	70	8
S021	G2	8.391				50	10		
S021_L	G3	8.394	42	0.12	80	50	20	80	10
S022	G1	8.390	15	0.02	100	19	6		
S023	G1	8.394	21	0.02	100	29	9		
S024	G1	8.394	22	0.04	100	31	9		
S027	G1	8.388	12	0.08	100	18	6		
S030	G2	8.386	28	0.01	36.5	40	10		
S031	G2	8.391	37	0.17	71.1	50	20		
S032	G1	8.391	41	0.07	100	60	20		

micrographs of incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed S011 (neutral pH, pre-mixed reactants) (Fig. 4 p) revealed a wide size distribution averaging 40(20) nm. These structures exhibited irregular faceting and appear to be formed by the aggregation of smaller primary particles. Table 2 summarizes the size parameters obtained from TEM analysis for all samples.

A notable morphological disparity was observed between the incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed S018 and S019, despite both being synthesized in neutral pH conditions. In S018 (pre-mixed reactants), TEM revealed large, well-defined trapezoidal structures (Fig. 4 a). In contrast, the sample S019 (delayed NaOH injection) exhibited a different morphology, with a notable absence of the extensive structures observed in S018 (Fig. 4 c). In the unwashed state of S019, particles initially averaged 60(20) nm. The subsequent washed counterpart (S019_L, Fig. 4 d) revealed a bimodal size distribution, characterized by the retention of larger features alongside a second, smaller population averaging 40(20) nm.

TEM micrographs of incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed S020 (Fig. 4 e) and S021 (Fig. 4 g) showed defined faceted morphologies. In contrast, the washed counterparts S020_L and S021_L (Fig. 4 f,h) appeared as products of aggregation and fusion units. This transition was accompanied by a broadening of the size distributions, with S020_L and S021_L revealing bimodal populations (e.g., ≈ 50 nm

Longer irradiation time or
Higher amount of precursor mass $\xrightarrow{\text{Extremely Strong (+)}}$ Larger crystallites / particles size

and ≈ 80 nm).

3.3.1.1. Complete sonochemical conversion. The impact of ultrasonic irradiation time was also analyzed via TEM for samples S030-S032 (Fig. 4 m-o). At incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed 10- and 20-min intervals (S030, S031), faceted nanoparticles were observed alongside residual oxyhydroxide structures. In the complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed 30-min sample (S032), well-defined faceted nanoparticles were the primary feature. The average size of the Fe_3O_4 fraction increased with irradiation time recorded at 40(10) nm (10 min), 50(20) nm (20 min), and 60(20) nm (30 min).

Alternatively, the effect of varying precursor concentration at a fixed irradiation time (10 min) was also evaluated via TEM (samples S022-S027, Fig. 4 i-l). Under these conditions, the synthesis yielded well-defined, faceted Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles with average sizes below 40 nm. An inverse correlation was observed between precursor concentration and average sizes (e.g., 18(6) nm for 0.4 mmol in S027 vs. 31(9) nm for 1.2 mmol in S024). Furthermore, these low-precursor samples exhibited narrower size distributions compared to the high-concentration series (S030-S032).

3.4. Statistical correlation of growth parameters

The relationship between synthesis conditions, particle size, and structural defectivity was evaluated using Pearson correlation coefficients (ρ) across three sample categories (Fig. 5, see Fig. S6 for extended scatter plots).

In the complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed group (Fig. 5 A), a strong positive correlation ($\rho \geq +0.94$) was recorded between effective irradiation time and Fe_3O_4 size (XRD and TEM). Simultaneously, the extremely strong correlation ($\rho \geq +0.98$) was observed between initial precursor mass and particle size. Size measurements for this group showed an internal consistency between XRD and TEM measurements techniques ($\rho = 0.998$).

In contrast, incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (Fig. 5 B) showed a moderate negative correlation between effective irradiation time and size ($\rho \leq -0.54$). The correlation between XRD mean size vs. TEM mean size correlation was $\rho = 0.78$, while incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed group decreased to $\rho = 0.25$.

The relationship between microstrain (ϵ) and size also varied by group (Fig. 5 C). The complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed group, exhibited a weak-to-moderate correlation ($\rho \leq +0.434$). However, strong positive correlations between microstrain and Fe_3O_4 size were recorded for both the incomplete sonochemical conversion/

Fig. 4. Transmission electron micrographs of sonochemically synthesized Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. Panels are arranged left-to-right across rows from top to bottom: Complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed: (i) S022; (j) S023; (k) S024; (l) S027; and (o) S032. Incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed: (a) S018; (c) S019; (e) S020; (g) S021; (m) S030; and (n) S031. Incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed: (b) S018_L; (d) S019_L; (f) S020_L; (h) S021_L; and (p) S011.

washed ($\rho \leq +0.795$) and unwashed ($\rho \leq +0.97$) groups.

3.5. Power absorption

Completing the structural and morphological characterization, the heating capacity of the nanoparticles under an alternating magnetic field (AMF) was evaluated via calorimetric measurements. To account for the multi-phase nature of the incomplete conversion samples, the absorbed power (P) was normalized by the total iron mass, defined as the Specific Power per Iron Mass (SPI).

3.5.1. Incomplete sonochemical conversion

Based on the screening of various frequencies and field amplitudes (Fig. 6 A), parameters of 760 kHz and 360 G were selected for subsequent measurements, as they yielded the highest heating efficiency. For all cases of incomplete sonochemical $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion, a significant increase in SPI was recorded following the washing procedure (Table 3). For example, the SPI rose from 164(3) in unwashed S021–455(7) $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in washed counterpart S021_L. In contrast, the SLP values, calculated using the Fe_3O_4 mass fraction derived from XRD, showed different trends during the washing process. In samples S018 and S019, the SLP decreased from 730(20) to 496(8) $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and from 480(10) to 437(7) $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively.

Fig. 5. Pearson Correlation Analysis of Synthesis Control and Structural Characteristics across Synthesis Groups. The triangular heatmaps show the pairwise Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) between five key parameters: effective irradiation time (t_{eff}), precursor mass (mPrec), microstrain (ϵ_{XRD}), crystallite size (d_{XRD}), and TEM mean size (d_{TEM}) for each group. (A) complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed, (B) incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed, and (C) incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed.

Fig. 6. Magnetic Heating Properties and Correlation Analysis Across Synthesis Groups. (A) Specific Loss Power (SLP) contour heatmap as a function of Magnetic Field and Frequency for sample S011. (B) Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) heatmap of structural characteristics and magnetic heating performance across the three distinct synthesis groups: complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed ("Pure" Unwashed), incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (Not "Pure" Unwashed), and incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed (Not "Pure" Washed). The matrix quantifies the pairwise correlation between: Specific Power per Iron Mass (SPI), microstrain (ϵ_{XRD}), crystallite size (d_{XRD}), and TEM mean size (d_{TEM}).

3.5.2. Complete sonochemical conversion

In the time-series samples (S030–S032), the SPI values for the incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (S030/S031) were higher than those recorded for the complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (S032), synthesized via extended ultrasonic irradiation. Furthermore, when evaluating the effect of varying precursor concentration at a fixed irradiation time (S022–S027, S032), an inverse relationship between SLP and size was observed (e.g., $381 \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for 18 nm in S027 vs. $99 \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for 60 nm in S032).

3.5.3. Non-ultrasonic conversion control

Larger crystallites/particles size $\xrightarrow{\text{Very Strong } (-)}$ Lower magnetic heating performance

To evaluate the influence of formation pathways on heating efficiency, a $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ control sample was prepared by the direct mixing of FeSO_4 and NaOH . Initially, the system exhibited an SPI of $17.1(3) \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in water. Upon immobilization in gelatin, the SPI increased to $30.0(4) \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Following a 3-minute ultrasonic treatment at 65°C , the SPI

reached $134(2) \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, a value comparable to the $137(2) \text{ W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ recorded for the 30-minute irradiated sample S032.

3.6. Statistical correlation of heating performance

The relationship between structural parameters and SPI was evaluated across the three sample groups (Fig. 6 B, see Fig. S7 for extended scatter plots). For the complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed group, the system exhibited a strong inverse dependence ($\rho \geq -0.82$) between Fe_3O_4 size and SPI ($= \text{SLP} \times 1.3820$).

In contrast, the correlation between size and heating efficiency was lower in the incomplete sonochemical conversion groups ($\rho \leq +0.52$). In these subsets, microstrain (ϵ) exhibited a stronger correlation with SPI ($\rho = 0.67$ for unwashed state and $\rho = 0.8$ for the washed counterpart).

Table 3

Experimental parameters measured and calculated for the determination of the SPI and the SLP. Samples are classified as complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (G1), incomplete sonochemical conversion/unwashed (G2), and incomplete sonochemical conversion/washed (G3). Control samples are shown separately and were not included in this classification. Symbols: maximum heating-curve slope $\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{\max}$, power (P); iron content (m_{Fe}); Specific Power per Iron mass (SPI); effective Fe_3O_4 fraction in the as-prepared product estimated from XRD (ϕ_{XRD}); and Specific Power Loss (SLP).

Sample ID	Description	$\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{\max}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	P (mW)	m_{Fe} (mg)	$\text{SPI} = \frac{P}{m_{\text{Fe}}}$ ($\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	ϕ_{XRD} (%)	SLP ($\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
Control_W	$\text{FeSO}_4 + \text{Na}(\text{OH})$ in water	37(8)	159(1)	9.3(1)	17.1(3)	–	12.4(2)
Control_G	$\text{FeSO}_4 + \text{Na}(\text{OH})$ in gelatine RT	60.8(9)	277.5(2)	9.3(1)	30.0(4)	–	21.7(3)
Control_GT	$\text{FeSO}_4 + \text{Na}(\text{OH})$ in gelatine 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	272(7)	1237(9)	9.3(1)	134(2)	–	97(2)
S011	G3	180(5)	710(3)	1.00(2)	710(10)	100	513(8)
S018	G2	37(1)	149.1(2)	0.296(5)	503(8)	50	730(20)
S018_L	G3	119(2)	483(1)	0.70(1)	690(10)	100	496(8)
S019	G2	37(2)	149.4(2)	0.454(7)	329(4)	50	480(10)
S019_L	G3	110.4(9)	445.9(4)	0.74(1)	600(10)	100	437(7)
S020	G2	28.7(7)	114.54(8)	0.394(6)	291(5)	50	420(10)
S020_L	G3	43.7(9)	174.7(2)	0.372(6)	470(7)	80	425(8)
S021	G2	11.9(8)	48.53(4)	0.297(5)	164(3)	50	237(8)
S021_L	G3	94(1)	375.4(4)	0.83(1)	455(7)	80	412(8)
S022	G1	79(2)	333.1(5)	0.83(1)	399(6)	100	289(5)
S023	G1	20(2)	80.5(1)	0.360(6)	224(4)	100	162(3)
S024	G1	34(1)	138.4(2)	0.75(1)	185(3)	100	134(2)
S027	G1	82(2)	323.7(8)	0.61(1)	527(9)	100	381(6)
S030	G2	43(1)	172.4(2)	0.98(2)	176(3)	37	350(10)
S031	G2	35.5(8)	144.5(1)	0.82(1)	175(3)	71	179(4)
S032	G1	24(1)	94.8(1)	0.69(1)	137(2)	100	99(1)

Higher crystal strain $\xrightarrow{\text{Strong (+)}}$ Higher magnetic heating performance

4. Discussion

4.1. Post-irradiation handling phase transformation

The macroscopic transition observation from a greenish, non-magnetic precipitate to a black magnetically responsive (Fig. 2 A) one suggests that Fe_3O_4 synthesis is not confined to the ultrasonic irradiation period but continues during the isolation steps, independent of the initial energy input. While the rapid reduction of the 1126 cm^{-1} band represents the passive removal of Na_2SO_4 byproduct, simultaneous intensification of the 574 cm^{-1} (Fe-O) band and the depletion of 3600 cm^{-1} hydroxyl content (with the OH:Fe-O peak depth ratio shifting from 1:5–1:25) provides a spectroscopic signature of the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion into Fe_3O_4 .

Two plausible competing pathways likely contribute to the necessary oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} :

Anaerobic Transformation (Schikorr Reaction): [39]

Aerobic oxidation:

Fe^{3+} generated by these mechanisms is subsequently consumed in the formation of magnetite-maghemite phases. This post-irradiation evolution presents a significant challenge: because the synthesis continues during handling, the washing steps themselves become a major variable that can hinder the reproducibility and precise phase control of the ultrasonic method.

The comparison between the incomplete sonochemical conversion series (S019) and complete conversion/unwashed samples (S023–S027, S032) suggest the existence of a sonochemical threshold. While S019 requires ten washing cycles to reach a high-purity spinel state, the S023–S032 series exhibits a 10th-wash-like spectrum immediately following irradiation (Fig. 2 C). This indicates that when the

sonochemical energy input is sufficient, the phase transformation is completed *in situ*. Conversely, below this threshold, the final properties of the nanoparticles are influenced by the post-irradiation handling rather than the ultrasonic parameters.

4.2. Sonochemical thresholds for phase purity

4.2.1. Incomplete sonochemical conversion under neutral pH conditions

The coexistence of Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$ in the unwashed neutral series (S018/S019) confirms that the sonochemical energy input was insufficient to bypass the formation of intermediate oxyhydroxide phases. The distinct preferential orientation of lepidocrocite, paired with the large trapezoidal structures observed via TEM in the pre-mixed S018 (Fig. 4 a), indicates that these oxyhydroxides act as advanced precursors that mature prior to sonochemical conversion. In contrast, the absence of such extensive structures in the delayed-injection S019 (Fig. 4 c) suggests that continuous sonication during precipitation effectively disrupts the organization of these precursors, though it does not eliminate them.

The transition to a pure spinel phase following the washing process demonstrates that this stage is a phase-completion process rather than a simple purification step. This is most evident in the bimodal size distribution that emerges in S019_L (Fig. 4 d); while the larger features from the unwashed state are retained, a significantly smaller secondary population emerges. This suggests that measurements of the unwashed state reflect a complex mixture where irregular oxyhydroxide phases are subsequently converted into smaller, more defined Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles during post-synthesis handling.

Ultimately, the irregular faceting and the appearance of units formed by the aggregation and fusion of smaller primary particles, as seen in S011 (Fig. 4 p), characterize the growth regime below the sonochemical threshold. These results confirm that in neutral pH conditions with incomplete irradiation, the final morphology is reshaped by post-irradiation phase-completion, where the conversion of remaining oxyhydroxides onto seeds governs the final particle dimensions and the resulting bimodal distribution.

4.2.2. Incomplete sonochemical conversion under high alkaline conditions

The transition to high alkaline conditions (S020/S021) fundamentally redirects the synthesis pathway, favoring the formation of trigonal $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and goethite intermediates rather than the lepidocrocite observed in neutral pH conditions (Fig. 3 b-e) [40]. This chemical environment significantly alters growth kinetics and structural relaxation, as evidenced by the preservation of a stoichiometric magnetite lattice parameter and a notable reduction in microstrain compared to the neutral pH series (S011–S019_L). TEM micrographs of the unwashed state (Fig. 4 e,g) reveal a more defined crystalline morphology compared to the irregular faceted nanoparticles of the neutral pH series (S011–S019), indicating that OH^- excess promotes the formation of more thermodynamically stable primary units during the early stages of irradiation.

However, this improved initial crystallinity does not prevent the bimodal size distributions and aggregation-based morphologies that emerge post-synthesis. The residual presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and goethite in the washed counterparts (S020_L/S021_L) suggests that the conversion of these alkaline-stabilized intermediates remains sensitive to the isolation process. The emergence of larger structures alongside primary seeds indicates that the subsequent conversion of this residual fraction occurs via the transformation and coalescence of precursors onto existing magnetite nuclei. This confirms that while alkalinity improves the initial faceting of the primary units, the final nanoparticle morphology in both neutral and alkaline conditions are heavily influenced by these post-irradiation aggregation steps.

4.2.3. Complete sonochemical conversion under high alkaline conditions

The synthesis of sonochemically phase-pure Fe_3O_4 is governed by a critical irradiation threshold, where the duration of ultrasonic treatment must be sufficient to facilitate the complete conversion of intermediate $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and oxyhydroxide phases. As demonstrated by the time-series (S030–S032), extending irradiation allows the system to transition from a mixture of faceted nanoparticles and residual precursors (Fig. 4 m-n) to a population dominated by well-defined nanocrystals (Fig. 4 o). This confirms that the phase purity observed in samples with shorter irradiation times (S011–S021) was not an intrinsic result of the sonochemical stage, but rather a consequence of post-irradiation transformations facilitated by the washing process. In these complete sonochemical conversion cases, the disappearance of intermediate phases indicates that the system reaches a state where crystal growth is likely governed by an Ostwald ripening mechanism [41]. This is supported by the increasing average nanoparticle size and the broadening of the size distribution observed with prolonged sonication, suggesting a dynamic growth regime rather than one limited by nucleation [42].

The alternative pathway to achieve complete sonochemical conversion reducing the initial precursor concentration (S022–S027), yields phase purity with significantly less irradiation time (Fig. 3 f). These conditions enable a more controlled nucleation and growth regime, resulting in faceted nanoparticles with significantly smaller sizes and narrower distributions. The inverse correlation between precursor concentration and average size confirms that while sufficient irradiation time acts as the primary kinetic driver for ensuring phase purity, the initial precursor mass serves as the primary thermodynamic control for the final particle dimensions. Ultimately, these results establish that reaching the sonochemical threshold is a mass-to-power dependent process; once this threshold is crossed, the synthesis yields stable nanocrystals that no longer rely on post-synthesis handling to reach their final phase and morphology.

4.3. Decoupling kinetic and thermodynamic drivers

The ability to isolate intrinsic ultrasonic chemistry from post-synthesis transformations relies on surpassing the sonochemical threshold. In the complete sonochemical conversion/unwashed group, the extremely strong correlations between size and both irradiation time

($\rho \geq +0.94$) and precursor mass ($\rho \geq +0.98$) establish a predictable dual-control pathway (Fig. 5 A). This confirms that once the phase transformation is complete *in situ*, the system operates in a robust regime where effective irradiation time acts as the primary kinetic control and precursor mass serves as the primary thermodynamic limit. The near-perfect agreement between XRD and TEM size measurements ($\rho = +0.998$) underscores the structural consistency of this group, indicating a singular, well-defined population of magnetite nanocrystals.

Conversely, the loss of systematic control in the incomplete conversion/unwashed groups highlights the instability inherent in the sub-threshold regime, where post-synthesis handling overrides the initial ultrasonic parameters. The moderate negative correlation observed for irradiation time ($\rho \leq -0.54$) indicates that without reaching the sonochemical threshold, time does not predictably dictate final particle size (Fig. 5 B). The most significant breakdown occurs in the correlation between XRD and TEM measurements for the washed samples ($\rho = 0.25$). This discrepancy serves as a quantitative measurement artifact of the post-synthesis converted Fe_3O_4 previously identified; the apparent TEM size is skewed by the inclusion of irregular defined oxyhydroxide precursors and a secondary Fe_3O_4 population, whereas XRD provides an average based only on the crystalline fraction.

This structural divergence is most clearly reflected in the relationship between size and microstrain (Fig. 5 C). While microstrain is only a minor byproduct of growth in the complete conversion group ($\rho \leq +0.434$), it becomes a dominant structural correlate in the incomplete conversion groups, reaching an extremely strong coupling ($\rho \leq +0.97$). Notably, the highest strain values ($\varepsilon \approx 0.25\%–0.41\%$) are concentrated in samples where $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion occurred in neutral pH conditions post-washing, whereas samples that evolved under the high alkalinity of the initial reaction medium exhibit lower strain ($0.01\% \leq \varepsilon \leq 0.17\%$). Paired with the observed bimodal TEM distributions, these findings identify microstrain as the primary structural fingerprint of the secondary formation pathway.

4.4. Magnetic heating performance

The AMF parameters for the calorimetric measurements (760 kHz and 360 G) were selected following an initial screening to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio across the wide structural variety of the conversion series. While the absence of independent AC susceptibility and anisotropy measurements precludes a rigorous Rosensweig/LRT fit, this high-frequency regime ensures that the magnetic power loss remains high across a broad distribution of relaxation times (τ). This setup serves as an empirical operating screen that effectively monitors Fe_3O_4 domains rather than a universal optimum [43].

We note that several samples were intentionally analyzed at intermediate stages of precursor conversion and washing; consequently, they do not represent structurally stationary end-products. Under these conditions, static magnetic parameters, such as saturation magnetization, coercive field, or AC susceptibility, would require immediate, stage-specific measurement to be rigorously correlated with the evolving phase composition and defect structure. Because these partially converted systems continue to evolve during post-synthesis handling, such static measurements were not incorporated into the experimental design and are considered beyond the tactical scope of this study.

Instead, the Specific Power per Iron Mass ($\text{SPI} = P/m_{\text{Fe}}$) is utilized as a more informative metric than SLP because the Fe_3O_4 fraction is still evolving during post-synthesis handling. The SPI serves as a functional monitor of the phase transformation; as the non-magnetic $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ precursor evolves into the spinel phase, the "inactive" iron is incorporated into the heating process. Consequently, the progressive increase in SPI observed across successive washing cycles serves as a macroscopic validation of the phase-completion and hydroxyl removal previously tracked via FTIR and XRD. This approach allows for a direct, normalized comparison between intrinsic sonochemical products and those evolved post-irradiation, bypassing the quantitative bias of a shifting magnetic

mass.

4.4.1. Functional impact from incomplete to complete sonochemical conversion

The evaluation of the incomplete sonochemical conversion series highlights the functional impact of the sonochemical threshold under the selected AMF parameters. In every instance of incomplete $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion, the SPI increased significantly following the washing process (e.g., rising from 164(3) to 455(7) $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in S021, Table 3), reflecting the incorporation of "inactive" iron into the magnetic heating process as residual precursors evolve into the spinel phase during post-irradiation handling.

The limitations of standard SLP normalization are explicitly evidenced by the contradictory trends observed in samples S018 and S019. In these cases, SLP values suggest an apparent decrease in heating efficiency after washing (e.g., from 730(20) to 496(8) $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), which directly conflicts with the observed increase in magnetic phase content. This discrepancy confirms that the XRD-derived Fe_3O_4 fraction, determined prior to washing and gelatin dispersion, fails to capture the actual magnetic mass present during the AMF measurement. By tracking the total heating capacity against a constant atomic iron mass, the SPI bypasses this quantitative uncertainty and reveals the true progression of the phase-purity threshold that static normalization obscures.

The evaluation of the complete-conversion series indicates a distinct relationship between the synthesis pathway and heating efficiency. In the time-series samples, the SPI for incomplete sonochemical conversions (S030/S031) was notably higher than for the sample where complete conversion was achieved through ultrasonic irradiation alone (S032). This suggests that the Fe_3O_4 domains formed during post-irradiation handling, i.e., through secondary low-energy conversion pathways, do not behave as fully equivalent magnetic entities to the better crystallized particles produced by prolonged sonication. It has been reported that the absorbed power depends critically on the effective anisotropy barrier governing moment reversal, in addition to particle size, saturation magnetization, and field conditions [44,45]. For magnetite, bulk room-temperature magnetocrystalline anisotropy is relatively low, with $K_1 \approx -1.1$ to -1.3×10^{-5} $\text{erg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, which is why Fe_3O_4 is generally considered a magnetically soft ferrite [46] and this increases the optimal particle size for heating to ≈ 30 – 40 nm [9]. Within this framework, our data are consistent with the view that the secondary Fe_3O_4 produced during washing develops a softer, or at least more favorably distributed, effective anisotropy barrier for the present AMF conditions than the more fully crystallized magnetite obtained after extended sonication. This interpretation is also compatible with previous sonochemical Fe_3O_4 studies in which the least crystallized sample exhibited the lowest K_{eff} ($\approx 2.4 \times 10^{-4}$ $\text{erg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) but the highest SLP in gelatin, whereas better crystallized magnetite reached a $K_{\text{eff}} \sim 1.05 \times 10^{-5}$ $\text{erg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and lower SLP values under the same immobilized conditions [7]. Consistently, in both our data and Ref [7], Brownian rotation was intentionally suppressed, so the measured heating reflects internal magnetic reversal rather than physical rotation of the particles. Therefore, the enhanced SPI/SLP observed here for samples dominated by washing-driven Fe_3O_4 growth could be interpreted as evidence that incomplete-conversion pathways generate Fe_3O_4 domains with an effective magnetic energy landscape more favorable for Néel-driven losses under the present field conditions [47–49].

When focusing specifically on Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles synthesized through complete $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion via ultrasonic irradiation (S022–S027, S032), the expected inverse relationship between SLP and size remains apparent (e.g., 381 $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ to 99 $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for 18 nm and 60 nm, respectively). These results indicate a trade-off: while low-energy conversion pathways favor higher magnetic performance, they retain undetermined non-magnetic phases that lead to an underestimation of SLP if not accounted via SPI. In contrast, while prolonged sonication reduces peak heating efficiency due to volume growth, it

remains the pathway for the precise tailoring of particle dimensions and structural consistency required to meet specific hyperthermia standards.

4.5. Structural drivers of magnetic heating efficiency

The statistical analysis of the heating performance demonstrates that the relationship between structural properties and power loss is fundamentally dictated by the degree of sonochemical conversion. For nanoparticles that reach the sonochemical threshold (complete sonochemical conversion), the system exhibits a strong inverse dependence ($\rho \geq -0.82$) between Fe_3O_4 crystallite size and power loss (Table 3, Fig. 6 B). This aligns with the principles of the Linear Response Theory (LRT) for systems where particle volume has surpassed the optimal relaxation threshold, leading to a size-dependent decrease in heating efficiency [50,51]. In this sonochemical phase-pure regime, the heating response is predictable, identifying particle volume as the primary structural predictor of performance.

In contrast, this size correlation breaks down in the incomplete sonochemical conversion groups ($\rho \leq +0.52$), where microstrain emerges as a more informative predictor of magnetic heating efficiency (ρ up to 0.8). Notably, the highest heating efficiencies are concentrated in samples where $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion occurred under neutral pH conditions post-washing (≈ 600 – 710 $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), which also correspond to the highest observed microstrain values. Samples that evolved under the high alkalinity of the initial reaction medium exhibit both lower microstrain and moderated SPI (≈ 450 – 470 $\text{W}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). While the absence of DC/AC magnetic measurements precludes the assignment of these trends to a specific relaxation mechanism, microstrain serves as a structural correlate of the observed heating, identifying the secondary formation pathway rather than a primary design parameter.

4.6. Synthesis roadmap and optimal conditions

In summary, these results define two distinct synthesis pathways governed by a critical sonochemical threshold. Optimal conditions for producing phase-pure, structurally consistent Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles are achieved at standard precursor concentrations with delayed NaOH injection and a minimum irradiation time (the sonochemical threshold) that scales with the precursor load. Surpassing this threshold ensures that the phase transformation is completed *in situ*, yielding a predictable growth regime and a systematic size-SLP correlation.

Conversely, termination of irradiation before complete conversion initiates a secondary pathway where residual $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ and oxyhydroxide precursors continue to react during post-synthesis handling. While these incomplete conversion pathways can yield high heating efficiencies, they result from an undetermined synthesis degree, making them less suitable for applications requiring high reproducibility and dimensional tailoring. In this sub-threshold regime, the SPI becomes the essential metric for tracking the evolving heating efficiency as precursors transform. Ultimately, this distinction clarifies why reaching the sonochemical threshold for $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ conversion is the key factor for ensuring protocol reproducibility and predictable magnetic performance.

5. Conclusions

Surpassing a sonochemical threshold for $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ complete conversion is the key factor for obtaining reproducible, phase-pure Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles. This work demonstrates that reaching this conversion threshold is governed by the interplay between precursor concentration and effective irradiation duration. Within the present reactor configuration, by maintaining a controlled NaOH injection, we establish that phase purity requires a minimum irradiation time of 10 min for low precursor concentrations (0.4–1.2 mmol), extending to at least 30 min for higher amounts (4 mmol). Our standardized three-stage protocol decouples intrinsic ultrasonic chemistry from post-synthesis

transformations, an effect largely overlooked in previous studies [7,13,20].

This distinction reveals that phase-pure sonochemical Fe₃O₄ follows predictable size-dependent SLP behavior. In contrast, when sonochemical conversion is incomplete, Fe(OH)₂ continues to transform during washing and dispersion; in these dynamic systems, SPI serves as a more informative metric than SLP because the Fe₃O₄ fraction is still evolving. In this context, the conclusions of the present work are supported by combined structural evidence (FTIR, XRD, TEM) and by direct calorimetric heating response under AMF. A full magnetic characterization of intermediate dynamic states would require a dedicated experimental design incorporating immediate stage-specific measurements and therefore remain outside the scope of the present study.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marco A. Morales Ovalle: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Enio Lima Jr.:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Gerardo F. Goya:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Gemini and ChatGPT to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and assume full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marco Antonio Morales Ovalle reports financial support was provided by H2020-MSCA NESTOR project (101007629). Marco Antonio Morales Ovalle reports financial support was provided by National Scientific and Technical Research Council. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.mtcomm.2026.115375](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2026.115375).

Data Availability

I have shared the link to my data in the attached manuscript.

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